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Exploring Factors Impacting the Repurchase Intention for Inter-City Vacation Travelers Traveling by Branded Bus Transportation Services in Egypt

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Abstract

Purpose: *To explore the key elements that determine the repurchase intention of branded bus services (Travel Tickets) among Egyptian vacation passengers who had previously traveled with a major market supplier.*

Design/methodology/approach: *A qualitative study with 9 industry experts was undertaken through in-depth interviews to validate the research model, followed by a quantitative survey with 222 respondents using non-probability convenience sampling. The qualitative data were analyzed using content analysis, and the quantitative data were analyzed using SPSS V.28*

Findings: *Three main variables: Perceived Value, Subjective Norms, and Service Availability positively impact the repurchase intention. Perceived Value has two dimensions: Functional and Symbolic. The functional comprises perceived quality, brand reputation, and perceived sacrifices. The symbolic covers the emotional, social, and bus appearance elements.*

Gender does not moderate Perceived Value, Subjective Norms, or Service Availability. Age moderates Subjective Norms, while it does not moderate Perceived Value or Service Availability

Practical implications – *Providing policymakers, executives, and marketers of transportation companies with an in-depth understanding of the significance of various variables influencing repurchase intention and perceived value for inter-city transportation for large buses for vacation travelers in Egypt, allowing them to have the right focus, tactics, and investment.*

Objectives:

- *Identifying and weighting elements that influence repurchase intention*
- *Identifying elements that impact perceived value and their corresponding weight.*
- *Investigating the impact of age and gender on the outcomes.*

Research Context - *The branded large buses used for inter-city transit in Egypt by vacationers. The large bus is more than 12 meters long and 3 meters tall.*

Paper type: *Research paper*

Key words: *Inter-City Transportation, Vacation Travelers, Perceived Value, Perceived Quality, Purchase, Re-Purchase, and the Egyptian Transportation Market*

INTRODUCTION

The topic of customer behavior, including the antecedents impacting purchasing behavior and brand choice, has been a central topic in marketing research since its inception. Over the last 50 years, various academic theories, literature, and frameworks have explored and investigated factors that impact different purchasing behaviors (Actual purchase, intention, and re-purchase). (Paz and Vargas, 2023). Some of these famous theories and models are **the theory of consumption values** by Sheth, Newman, & Gross (1991); **the means-end Model** originally by Dodds and Monroe (1985) and revisited by Zeithaml (1988); **the theory of buyer behavior** by

Howard and Sheith (1969); **the theory of reasoned action** by Ajzen and Fishbein (1975); **Holbrook's Typology of Consumer Values** by Holbrook (1999); **Consumer Decision Model** by Howard (1989); **PERVAL Model** introduced by Sweeney and Soutar (2001); **SERV-PERVAL** proposed by Petrick (2002); **Stimulus-Response Model – Black Box Model of Kotler (1997)**; **the theory of planned behavior** proposed by Ajzen (1991).

Despite the strategic weight of intercity bus transportation in Egypt, where millions rely on it each year, no academic study has been performed to address the repurchase intention behavior for vacation travelers for brand bus. This study adds to the academic literature by providing a theoretical framework for addressing the topic in Egypt, as well as laying the way for more in-depth studies on consumer behavior for ground transportation passengers in Egypt.

THEORITICAL BACKGROUND

A. Repurchase intention

Repurchase intention refers to a consumer's plan to rebuy the same product or the service again from the same company. (Ying-Feng Kuoa, Wub, & Dengc, 2009; Hellier, Geursen, Carr, & Rickard, 2003)

B. Perceived Value

The perceived value refers to the assessment made by the customer for the total value by comparing and weighing the perceived benefits vs. the perceived costs (Zhang, Liu, Zhang, & Pang, 2021; Zeithaml, 1988; Sanchez & Iniesta, 2007; Blut, Chaney, Lunardo, Mencarelli, & Grewal, 2023; Verleye, Hatak, Koller, Zauner, & Zeithaml, 2020). The positive effect of perceived value on service selection, purchasing behavior (actual, intended, or repurchase) has been explicitly articulated and demonstrated in the academic literature by many well-known marketing scholars and researchers. (Petrick J. , 2002; Zeithaml, 1988; Sweeney, Soutar, & Johnson, 1999; Bajs, 2015)(Tanrikulu, 2021; Bahoo, Umar, Mason, & Zamparo, 2023)(Wollenberg & Waty, 2017; Basaran & Aksoy, 2017; Winasis & Sembel, 2023)

H1: Perceived Value has a positive impact on repurchase intention

C. Subjective Norms

They refer to the opinions and recommendations of trustworthy people, friends, and family to consumers regarding the service. (Trafimow, 2009; Hagger, 2019; Wirth & C. Maier, 2019; Melnyk, Carrillat, & Melnyk, 2022). Academic theories such as the Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 1991) and Theory of Reasoned Action (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975) along with a multitude of different respectable researchers in different industries, including tourism (Gallarza & Gil, 2008), transportation (Ramadani, Armutcu, Reshidi, Tan, & İnce, 2024) (Han, Wang, Zhao, & Li, 2017) , and consumer electronics (Rai & Budhathoki, 2023) have explicitly illuminated the positive relationship between subjective norms and different behavioral actions, such as purchase intention, and actual purchase. The relationship with the re-purchase behavior was also highlighted in different studies. (Hsu, Chang, & Chuang; Söderlund & Oikarinen, 2018)

H4: Subjective Norms have a positive effect on repurchase intention

D. Service Availability

The impact of product unavailability on different behavioral actions, such as purchase thoroughly discussed in the academic literature. Many theories and frameworks clarified this relationship, including commodity theory, conformity theory, regret theory, and reactance theory. (Barton, Zlatevska, & Oppewal, 2022). The effect of service availability on repurchase was also stated in different studies. (Blut, Chowdhry, Mittal, & Brock, 2015; Yen & Lu, 2008)

H7: Desired Service Class availability has a positive effect on repurchase intention

E. Moderator Variables

Age and Gender are frequently used as moderators, influencing the strength and path between independent and dependent variables in consumer behavior research

H2: Age moderates the relationship between perceived value and repurchase intention

H3: Gender moderates the relationship between perceived value and repurchase intention

H5: Age moderates the relationship between subjective norms and repurchase intention

H6: Gender moderates the relationship between subjective norms and repurchase intention

H8: Age moderates the relationship between Desired Service Class availability and repurchase intention

H9: Gender moderates the relationship between Desired Service Class availability and repurchase intention

Research Model

Figure 1 by the author

1. Dimensions of Perceived Value

A. Perceived Quality

It is the overall personal subjective assessment of the consumer of the excellence and benefits of the service against its costs. (Zeithaml, 1988; Stylidis, Wickman, & Söderberg, 2019; Mitra & Golder, 2006). Perceived quality impacts the perceived value, as clearly stated by different researchers and in the Means-End Model. (Zeithaml, 1988) (Bajs, 2015; Petrick J. F., 2004) (Teas & Agarwal, 2000)

B. Perceived Sacrifices

It is all the sacrifices and costs that the consumer pays and bears to buy the service. The cost could be the money paid to buy the product, and it could be non-monetary, such as the effort, the convenience, and the time spent to get our use of the service. (Mencarelli & Arnaud, 2012), (Wong, Ling, & Sia, 2020). Perceived Sacrifices impact the perceived value negatively. (Zeithaml, 1988; Petrick J. , 2002; Wang, Lo, Chi, & Yang, 2004).

C. Intrinsic attributes

Intrinsic attributes are the built-in features that cannot be changed without changing physical elements of the product itself, such as size, color, or appearance. (Zeithaml, 1988). They give the customer a signal of the quality of the product or the service.(Creusen & Schoormans, 2004; Dou, Li, Nan, Wang, & Zhou, 2021; Zeithaml, 1988) .

Color impacts the perception of consumers on value and increases the intention to buy. (Kato, 2022). Product appearance impacts different dimensions as well, such as the consumer perception of quality, value, and purchase intentions. (Kato, 2022) . Product appearance, as an intrinsic attribute, has been proven in different research to have a positive impact on multiple dimensions such as perceived quality, value, and customer choice.

The qualitative study of this research further buttressed the academic research regarding the importance of intrinsic cues on the repurchase intention for inter-city transportation, focusing on the importance of the general appearance and the color of the bus

D. Extrinsic attributes

They refer to the external elements that are associated with the service, but not physically. For example, brand name, price, and brand reputation. (Zeithaml, 1988; Dodds & Monroe, 1991) warranties (Zeithaml, 1988), and the country of origin. (Espejel, Fandos, & Flavian, 2007). Extrinsic attributes have a positive impact on perceived value. (Zeithaml, 1988; Dodds & Monroe, 1991; Petrick J. F., 2004; Alhamdina & Hartono, 2023).

The qualitative study of this study showed the importance of brand reputation, as an extrinsic attribute. This is aligned with the literature that highlighted the weight of brand reputation and its impact on different behavioral dimensions, including perceived value. (Zeithaml, 1988; Dodds & Monroe, 1991; Petrick J. F., 2004; Vuong, Tushar, Voak, Huan, & Dung, 2024; Mansoor, Saeed, Kartawinata, & Khan, 2022).

Brand reputation represents to the customer, the invisible warranty and guarantee of the product quality, value they enjoy by owning the product or using the service. (Alhamdina & Hartono, 2023; Singh, Singh, & Parmar, 2024)

E. Emotional values

Emotional values imply the sentiments that the consumer associates with the product or the services (Tanrikulu, 2021). The literature underlined the considerable impact of emotional values on perceived value (Park & Kim, 2017; Ofir Turel, 2010).

F. Social values

Social Value represents the amalgamation of “status” plus “esteem”. It is related to how the brand supports feelings of recognition and pride. (Dodds & Monroe, 1991; Holbrook, 1999) . It pertains to the value given by the product to the customer sociably when buying or using the product. In other words, how the purchase of this product is perceived socially by others, and how the product supports upgrading the customer’s social perception about himself compared to others. (Sweeney & Soutar, 2001; Petrick J. , 2002; Walsh, Shiu, & Hassan, 2014)

The literature has extensively emphasized the positive effect of social value on perceived value. (Sweeney & Soutar, 2001; Holbrook, 1999) This relationship was underscored in the model of perceived value – PERVAL. (Sweeney & Soutar, 2001) and Holbrook’s Typology of Consumer Value. (Holbrook, 1999) .

Dimensions of Perceived Value

Figure 2 by the author

Dimensions of Perceived Quality

The SERVQUAL model suggests 5 main attributes to measure the perceived quality: Reliability, Assurance, Empathy, Tangibility, and Responsiveness. (Parasuraman, Zeithaml, & Berry, 1985)

Reliability refers to the consistency in delivering the promised services correctly, and hence, consumers can trust and depend on this service. (Parasuraman, Zeithaml, & Berry, 1985; Islam, Chowdhury, Sarker, & Ahmed, 2014). Examples of reliability in public transportation: Punctuality of arrival and departure timing (Randheer, AL-Motawa, & J, 2011; Mikhaylov, Gumenyuk, & Mikhaylova, 2015), along with informing the customers properly of any modification in the timing of the trip. (Garvin, 1987). In addition to the recurrence of bus breakdowns and accidents. (Memic, Vasiljevic, Tanackov, & Stevie, 2018).

Assurance refers to the capabilities, skills, and knowledge of the staff to instigate confidence in the quality of service. (Berry, Parasuraman, & Zeithaml, 1988; Awasthia, Satyaveer, Omranic, & Panahi, 2011). For example, the skills of the driver, the abidance by a professional driving style, and his knowledge about the routes. (Mikhaylov, Gumenyuk, & Mikhaylova, 2015).

Empathy refers to the attitude of the front-line workers, such as drivers, sales agents, and customer service representatives, toward customers. It reflects how much they care and pay attention. (Berry, Parasuraman, & Zeithaml, 1988; Kamil, Azman, Soraya, Hanan, & Suhaila, 2019). Good examples are the driver's attitude in helping passengers. (Mikhaylov, Gumenyuk, & Mikhaylova, 2015).

Tangibility refers to the physical evidence associated with a service, such as facilities, tools, equipment, and the look of the staff. (Parasuraman, Zeithaml, & Berry, 1985; Govender, 2016). Some examples of tangibility in public transportation: Bus cleanliness. (Randheer, AL-Motawa, & J, 2011). It has been acknowledged by different scholars as the highest weighty factor for tangibility (Kamil, Azman, & Hanan, 2019). Air conditioning, the temperature inside the bus, and the bus's appearance. (Mikhaylov, Gumenyuk, & Mikhaylova, 2015).

Responsiveness infers the ability of employees to provide good and fast service. (Parasuraman, Zeithaml, & Berry, 1985). For example, how responsive the call center representative, the complaints team, or the driver is to the inquiries or complaints of passengers. (Mikhaylov, Gumenyuk, & Mikhaylova, 2015)

METHODOLOGY

The research method adopted was a Mixed Method, as the research started with a qualitative study through in-depth interviews with 9 Interviewees, then it was followed by a quantitative study. This method is widely applied in consumer behavioral research, as it helps the researcher to comprehend the research problems deeply and get insights about the factors that can impact it. (Creswell J. , 2014).

For the qualitative study, the method of data collection was in-depth interviews, which is a commonly acknowledged method for qualitative studies. (DiCicco-Bloom & Crabtree, 2006). This method helps the researcher to have honest, open, and unbiased opinions from the interviewees (King, Horrocks, & Brooks, 2018). The interviewees were industry experts in the bus transportation industry. The number of interviewees was 9. This number is sufficient for getting the required insights, as different authors have set 5 as the minimum number for exploratory research. (Saunders, et al., 2018), while others debated that the number should be 6 to reach the basic ideas.(Guest, Bunce, & Johnson, 2006).

The interviews took around 30 minutes, and the researcher documented the answers of the interviewees. The interviewees were chosen according to ease of access, availability, and their relevance to the research, which is considered a convenience sampling technique. (Marshall & Rossman, 2016; Creswell J. , 2014)

All questions were generated from existing literature in English, then translated into Arabic to make it easier for the Egyptian interviewees to clearly understand the questions. The Time Horizon is Cross-Sectional. The data analysis technique adopted was Content Analysis. It is a well-known technique used for qualitative studies. (Krippendorff, 2019)

The researcher had 3 steps: Data organization to detect relevant sentences to the topic. The unit of analysis is the individual interviewee, then 1uestions were written in a column, and in another column, the expressive sentences stated by interviewees were in another column, finally, Theme-oriented analysis was used in decoding themes. (Clarke & Braun, 2006)

For the quantitative study, the data collection method used was a survey and questionnaires. This is aligned with the nature of this research. This method is a very eminent in social research. (Kothari, 2004; Alghamdi, 2017; Manion, Morrison, & Cohen, 2017) , and thought of as the ideal for consumer behavior research. (Malhotra, 2010). The respondents were asked to answer the questions by marking their agreement from 1 to 5, with 1 being strongly disagree, and 5 strongly agree. The 1 to 5 scale is a Likert Scale, which is a highly accepted and validated psychometric technique to measure the opinions of consumers. (Joshi, Saket, Chandel, & Pall, 2015)

Questions of the survey were taken from the literature, except for the question related to the bus appearance, which was developed by the researcher. The questions were translated from English to Arabic to fit the respondents, as their first language is Arabic. It was web-based and printed as well as a hard copy. The Time Horizon of the study is Cross-Sectional. The researcher gathered the responses of every respondent at one time and not over different periods. (Setia, 2016; Creswell J. , 2014). No population frame available, as a result, a non-probability sampling technique was used with a convenience sampling technique. It is a well-known technique in consumer behavior research from a hand (Bryman, 2016), and cost/time-effective from another hand. (Etikan, Musa, & Alkassim, 2015). The sample size according to the 10-times rule is 90. (Islam, Ghani, & Jauhar, 2016). According to Power Analysis Using G*Power: 100 respondents with Effect size (f^2): 0.35, Power ($1 - \beta$): 0.90, Significance level – Alpha (α): 0.05. (Faul, Erdfelder, Buchner, & Lang, 2009; Hair, Hult, & Sarstedt, 2022). The researcher gathered 222 surveys: 50 for the Pilot then 172 for the core study. The respondents enjoyed 50 EGP upon completing the survey. The data collection took 7 months to be completed.

Validity: The questionnaire was translated into Arabic using the Back-Translation practice. The translation was done by the researcher, who is an Arabic native speaker. In addition, the Arabic version has reviews by an Academic professor and different doctoral researchers. Besides, questions were obtained from the literature.

Internal Reliability was measured by Cronbach's alpha, with a minimum threshold of 0.7

RESULTS

Qualitative Study

Theme 1: Perceive Value as a Factor Influencing Repurchase intention

Nine out of nine interviewees consistently highlighted the importance of perceived value as a decisive factor in selecting the bus brand. This theme confirms the literature and justifies the inclusion of the construct in the framework

Theme 2: Subjective Norms as a Variable Impacting Repurchase intention

Six out of 9 interviewees stressed the weight of friends and family recommendations on the final repurchase intention. The findings align with the literature and validate the addition of the variable in the framework

Theme 3: Service Availability impacts Repurchase intention positively

The availability of the desired service class at the required time plays a pivotal role in the consumer's for repurchase intention. Five out of Nine interviewees stated this relationship explicitly. The findings are in line with the academic literature and authenticate the insertion of the construct in the theoretical framework.

Theme 4: Dimensions of Perceived Value

The dimensions of Perceived Value are six dimensions: Perceived Quality, Perceived Sacrifices had 9 out of 9, followed by Brand Reputation (5 Interviewees), Emotional Value, Bus Appearance (3 Interviewees), and finally Social Value (2 Interviewees). The findings justify testing the 9 factors as a dimension for Perceived Value, and are fully aligned with academic literature

Theme 5: Dimensions of Perceived Quality

Five main dimensions for perceived quality aligning with Serv-Qual: Reliability, Tangibles, were stated by most of the interviewees as main dimensions of the perceived quality, followed by Responsiveness, Assurance, and finally, empathy was mentioned by two interviewees

Quantitative Study

Normality Tests

All constructs of the study are not normally distributed, and the Kolmogorov–Smirnov and Shapiro–Wilk tests revealed $p < .001$, showing statistical significance. As a result, the data is considered non-normally distributed due to the general pattern of non-normality.

Reliability Test: Cronbach's alpha was used to assess the internal consistency reliability for all constructs, and for item total statistics

Results of Reliability Test

No	Construct	Cronbach's Alpha	Range of Corrected Item-Total Correlation
1	Repurchase Intention	.858	.546 - .852
2	Perceived Value	.784	.608 - .645
3	Service Availability	.713	.332 - .570
4	Subjective Norms	.725	.374 - .622
5	Perceived Quality	.860	.683 - .754
6	Perceived Sacrifices	.852	.576 - .732
7	Bus Appearance	.784	.653 - .653
8	Brand Reputation	.797	.363 - .787
9	Emotional Value	.950	.830 - .889
10	Social Value	.914	.799 - .884
11	Tangibles	.702	.392 - .517
12	Service Reliability	.720	.157 - .633
13	Assurance	.702	.486 - .558
14	Empathy	.766	.345 - .706
15	Responsiveness	.857	.751 - .751

Table 1 by the author

All constructs have acceptable reliability above 0.7. The minimum value for the range for Corrected Item-Total Correlation exceeded 0.3 for all constructs, except for Service Reliability, showing that items contributed importantly to the construct. Service Reliability showed an acceptable reliability coefficient, but there was one item that scored 0.157. However, "Cronbach's alpha if item deleted" reveals that the removal of this item would lead to a negligible change in the overall reliability score for the construct.

Correlation among the Dimensions of Perceived Value

Five out of the six dimensions of Perceived Value show good correlation with Perceived Value, with clear strong correlation between Perceived Value and Perceived Quality ($\rho = .633$, $p < .01$), and Perceived Value with Emotional Value ($\rho = .548$, $p < .01$). Bus Appearance, and Perceived Value did not have a statistically significant correlation ($\rho = .071$, $p > .05$)

Perceived Quality showed strong correlation with Perceived Value, Brand Reputation, Perceived Sacrifices, and Emotional Value. Perceived Sacrifices had a suitable correlation with Perceived Quality, Brand Reputation, and Perceived Value. Bus Appearance showed a weak correlation with all other variables. Brand Reputation

revealed a good correlation with Perceived Quality, Perceived Value, Perceived Sacrifices, and Emotional Value. Social Value showed a moderate correlation with Perceived Value and Emotional Value

Correlation among the Dimensions of Perceived Quality

Perceived Quality has a good correlation with all its dimensions, notably, a strong one with Empathy ($\rho = .508$, $p < .01$), followed by Reliability ($\rho = .487$, $p < .01$), Assurance ($\rho = .451$, $p < .01$), Tangibles $\rho = .450$, $p < .01$), and finally, Responsiveness ($\rho = .378$, $p < .01$),

Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) of Perceived Value

The result of The Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin (KMO) is 0.758, showing sufficient fitness for factor analysis. In addition, Bartlett's Test of Sphericity revealed statistically significant results, $\chi^2(15) = 340.383$, $p < .001$. As a result, the correlation matrix is proper for Exploratory Factor Analysis. **Principal Component Analysis (PCA)** was used to conduct the factor extraction. The rotated solution utilized **Varimax rotation with Kaiser normalization**, and concluded in 3 iterations. Factor retention was regulated by the **eigenvalue-greater-than-one rule**

Results of Rotated Component Matrix for Factor Analysis of Perceived Value

	Component	
	1	2
Perceived Quality	.892	
Brand Reputation	.860	
Perceived Sacrifices	.791	
Emotional Value	.702	.376
Bus Appearance		.770
Social Value		.684

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization^a

a. Rotation converged in 3 iterations.

Table 2 by the author

Perceived Value had originally six different dimensions. The EFA implies that Perceived Value consists of two high-order dimensions:

Functional, which included robust loading on Perceived Sacrifices (0.791), Perceived Quality (0.892), Brand Reputation (0.860), and reflected the functional aspects of the service.

Symbolic Value, which comprises the emotional feelings and social sides of the service. It has sound loadings for Social Value (0.684), Emotional Value (0.702), and Bus Appearance (0.770),

Hypothesis Testing – Regression Analysis

To test the hypothesis, a simple linear regression analysis was implemented with the three main independent variables and the dependent variable (Repurchase intention).

1. Perceive Value and Repurchase Intention

Perceived Value and Repurchase Intention Regression

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.759 ^a	.576	.573	.500

a. Predictors: (Constant), Perceived Value

Table 3 by the author

The above table shows a robust overall fitting with very strong explanatory power for perceived value. The Std Error of the estimate implies an adequate level of prediction precision.

ANOVA Test for Perceived Value and Repurchase Intention

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	57.657	1	57.657	230.883	.000 ^b
1 Residual	42.453	170	.250		
Total	100.110	171			

a. Dependent Variable: Repurchase Intention

Table 4 by the author

In addition, the ANOVA test of $F(1, 170) = 230.883$, $p < .001$ shows a statistical significance

H1 is supported, confirming that perceived value has a significant and positive impact on repurchase intention.

2. Service Availability and Repurchase Intention

Service Availability and Repurchase Intention Regression

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.593 ^a	.351	.348	.618

a. Predictors: (Constant), Service Availability

Table 5 by the author

The above table shows a good fit of the model, implying that service availability is a good predictor for the repurchase intention, yet with a relatively lower power than the perceived value. The standard error of the estimate (.618) shows a satisfactory level of predictive accuracy.

ANOVA Test for Service Availability and Repurchase Intention

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	35.178	1	35.178	92.099	.000 ^b
Residual	64.933	170	.382		
Total	100.110	171			

a. Dependent Variable: Repurchase Intention

b. Predictors: (Constant), Service Availability

Table 6 by the author

The ANOVA test proves the significance of the regression model $F(1, 170) = 92.099, p < .001$

H7 is supported, confirming that service availability has a significant and positive effect on repurchase intention.

3. Subjective Norms and Repurchase Intention**Subjective Norms and Repurchase Intention Regression**

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.550 ^a	.303	.299	.641

a. Predictors: (Constant), Subjective Norms

Table 7 by the author

The results reveal a moderate model fit, signifying that subjective norms has the lower level of impact on repurchase intention than the perceived value and service availability. Yet, it is considered a good predictor. The standard error of the estimate (.641) gives a satisfactory precision for prediction

ANOVA Test for Subjective Norms and Repurchase Intention

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	30.305	1	30.305	73.801	.000 ^b
Residual	69.806	170	.411		
Total	100.110	171			

a. Dependent Variable: Repurchase Intention

b. Predictors: (Constant), Subjective Norms

Table 8 by the author

The results of the ANOVA test demonstrate that the regression model is significant, $F(1, 170) = 73.801, p < .001$.

H4 is supported, confirming that subjective norms exert a significant and positive influence on repurchase intention.

Multiple Regression Analysis

Results of Multiple Regression Analysis

Figure 3 by the author

According to the ANOVA test, the regression model is clearly significant, $F(3, 168) = 91.756, p < .001$, The standard error of the estimate (.475) highlights a good level of accuracy for prediction.

Moderators: Age & Gender

To test whether age & gender moderate the relationships between Perceived Value, Service Class Availability, and Subjective Norms with Repurchase intention, PROCESS Macro (Model 1) Was conducted with a 5,000 bootstrap sample. (Hayes, 2022)

Results of Moderation Analysis

Hypothesis	Result	p-value
H2: Age moderates the relationship between perceived value and repurchase intention	Not Supported	.473
H3: Gender moderates the relationship between perceived value and repurchase intention	Not Supported	.361
H5: Age moderates the relationship between subjective norms and repurchase intention	Supported	Significant Relationship Younger Age: (b = .44, t = 3.68, p < .001). Older Age: (b = .85, t = 9.08, p < .001). Subjective norms have a higher impact on the repurchase intention of younger customers than older ones
H6: Gender moderates the relationship between subjective norms and repurchase intention	Not Supported	.812
H8: Age moderates the relationship between Desired Service Class availability and repurchase intention	Not Supported	.892
H9: Gender moderates the relationship between Desired Service Class availability and repurchase intention	Not Supported	.075

Table 9 by the author

Discussion and conclusion

This study explored the antecedents of the repurchase intention for vacation travelers who use branded large buses to travel between cities, and the moderating effects of age and gender on these factors. It also dug deeply into the dimensions of perceived value, as one of the most important factors impacting the repurchase intention. The results of this study highlighted that three focal factors impact the repurchase intention: Perceived Value, Subjective Norms, and Service Availability. Perceived Value contributes to the strongest influence, followed by service availability, then Subjective Norms. The results are aligned with previous general consumer behavior studies about factors impacting purchase, where perceived value was one of the determinants of the repurchase intention in different studies. (Zeithaml, 1988; Petrick J. , 2002). Subjective Norms were considered a solid factor impacting different purchase behaviors in other studies. (Ajzen, 1991; Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975), and service availability was considered one of the elements impacting the purchase, and re purchase intention in the literature. (Weissmann & Hock, 2021) . With the lack of literature about the factors impacting repurchase intention for the tickets of branded buses for vacation travelers in Egypt, this study illuminated a new theoretical framework, showing and testing these factors and their impact.

In addition, the original model used in this study suggested four main dimensions for perceived value: Intrinsic and extrinsic attributes, perceived quality, and perceived sacrifices. (Zeithaml, 1988) With the qualitative study, the researcher suggested six dimensions: Intrinsic (Bus Appearance), Extrinsic (Brand Reputation), Perceived Quality, Perceived Sacrifices, Social Value, and Emotional Value. The two additional variables were supported by literature in different researchers, social value (Sweeney & Soutar, 2001; Holbrook, 1999), and emotional value. (Kumar, Lee, & Kim, 2009)

According to the results of this study, the initial six dimensions of Perceived Value were grouped into two main dimensions: Functional and Symbolic. The functional dimension signifies the perceived superiority of the service, including its quality, reputation, price, time, and efforts exerted to get the service. The symbolic dimension reflects the affective elements, including the social, emotional, and visual aspects of the bus. Gender did not moderate the relationship between perceived value, service availability, or subjective norms and repurchase intention. Age also did not moderate the relationship between repurchase intention and either perceived value or service availability; however, age moderated the relationship between subjective norms and repurchase intention, where younger ages were more impacted by subjective norms than older ones. This study carries several implications for decision makers in transportation companies, policy makers, and academics as well. The empirical conclusions of this research answer the main questions related to the repurchase intention with its factors, giving a clear regression model for predicting the impact on repurchase intention. It illuminated the knowledge with a new theoretical framework dedicated to the transportation industry in Egypt, with focused perceived value dimensions. It also clarified the correlation between the suggested dimensions for perceived quality and perceived quality from a hand, and with each other from another hand. Moreover, it tested age and gender as moderating variables, giving a new insight into the effect of age on the relationship between subjective norms and repurchase intention. The decision makers in transportation companies can capitalize on this model to have the right strategy in place, putting the right investment, focus, and efforts on the right elements, while predicting the impact on repurchase intention. They can also link their marketing programs to age and friends' recommendations.

Limitations & Future Research:

Investigating the city of the respondent as a moderating variable, investigating the effect of other extrinsic variables on perceived value, investigating the effect of other intrinsic variables on perceived value, identifying the dimensions of Perceived Quality, investigating the effect of some variables such as perceived quality, and perceived sacrifices, directly on re-purchase intention, conducting this study on Micro-Bus customers, and conducting this study on Business/Education Travelers.

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